

STORAGE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE ECO-SYSTEM

2nd TNA Call Documentation - User

STORIES TNA2 POST RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE (WITH SATISFACTION SURVEY): USER (S)

General information about the project	
Project title (as used in application)	Hierarchical Control Strategies of Multi-Storage Systems Energy
Project acronym (max 15 characters)	HARNESSER
StoRIES TNA RI(s) accessed	PROTEAS - The Cyprus Institute, Cyprus
Keywords (up to ten, free text)	Thermal sensible Storage, Batteries, Micro-grid, annual modelling, Machine Learning
Arrival date (in town where RI located)	25/11/2023
Departure date (from town where RI located)	8/12/2023
Starting date of access (first day at RI)	27/11/2023
Finishing date of access (last day at RI)	7/12/2023
Number of days not using the RI (during the above period)	4 days
Reason for not using RI those days (describe)	weekend
Number of days using the RI	9 days
Number of users granted access (group size)	1 person
Comments	
Access Summary Report - work performed and initial results	
Brief description of the objectives of your project (up to 200 words)	
<p>This project concerns with the implementation of a hierarchical control strategies on a hybrid renewable energy power plant (PROTEAS plant in Cyprus) with a multi-energy storage system (TES). The plant involves central receiver system (CRS), 35 kWp photovoltaic panels (PV), 10 kW wind turbine and two 10 kWp dish-Stirling, while the storage systems are based on a sensible heat unit (14 tons of solar salts) and electro-chemical batteries (50 batteries of 108 kWh of capacity). This facility is able to produce electricity for the national grid and its self-consumption. The</p>	

hierarchical control strategy is divided into three layers: the top layer (management layer) is responsible for the system's overall stability, and scheduling optimization that requires balancing electricity generation and load demand to ensure the safety and stability of electricity production and user demand. The second layer is responsible for determining the optimal setpoint for each of the renewable energy technologies. The power control and voltage stability are handled at the third layer. The work was carried out in TRNSYS software with the built-in TMY library adapted to the PROTEAS location (Akrotiri weather station for the wind and temperature, solargis for the radiations).

Activities performed (up to 600 words)

- Visiting PROTEAS plant in Cyprus and sharing of technical information about the facility in terms of the different existing renewable energy technologies, ways of integration, storage components, micro-grid power, desalination process and control systems.
- Simulating the behaviour of the different components within TRNSYS (Simulation Studio): PV panels, wind turbine, solar receiver with heliostat field performance, two parabolic dishes, battery storages, thermal storages and the power electronics for control.
- Optimisation of the management of the electric heaters' operation (hybrid storage) in sequence based on the state of charge of the batteries and the molten salts average temperature.
- Producing annual energy performance assessment based on Typical Meteorological Year weather data

Scientific results (up to 800 words)

The program consisted in a knowledge exchange about hybridised storage system actually at the premises of the Cyprus Institute in PROTEAS. The technical info was exchanged in parallel to the modelling in TRNSYS. The common activity was tuned around the optimisation of the heaters' operation immersed into the molten salts storage tank. The control is hierarchical in order to extend the end of life of the batteries (no further depletion than 30%).

The excess of electricity is sent to the grid if the different elements of the hybrid storage are full.

The common activity has been centred around the optimisation of the flow of energy to the heaters and will be extended further on the future of the whole system.

Interpretation of the results (up to 400 words)

The results demonstrated that the sequential activation of the heaters would erase the need for the electricity from the national grid. Thus, auxiliaries are covered by the micro-grid itself. Also, the Carnot type battery helps to extend the window of operation of the steam turbine, by maintaining a suitable average temperature of the storage medium: molten salts that freeze at 240 degrees.

Main achievements during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

The main achievement is the proposal for electricity consumption reduction from the grid for the auxiliaries. This is an important element for CSP plants in general as the electric consumption for auxiliaries decrease the power output to the grid and thus decreases the potential incomes. Hybrid storage supported by a poly-generative micro-grid as in PROTEAS also further increase the dispatchability potential to better respond to sudden peaks in the national grid.

Difficulties during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

The access to the facility was clear providing deep details of the different component of the site as well as its basic modelling. The modelling has been transferred to the visitor so the collaboration can continue beyond the physical access.

Intended publications

A common publication is intended to be submitted to a scientific journal (Elsevier Solar Energy, MDPI Energies, Elsevier Renewable energies, MDPI Sustainability, etc.). This will be done during 2025.

Data management

The Data will be shared between the Cyprus Institute and the Helwan University, exclusively. The latter will not share the Data collected during the TNA to a third part. The potential common

publication(s) will be co-authored by representative of both institutions, who have contributed to the research activity stemming from the TNA.

Conclusions / additional comments

The TNA was the scope of initial exchange between the 2 institutions for a better understand of the micro-grid in place and its hybrid storage. The modelling has been improved in order to minimise the electricity consumption of the auxiliaries taking advantage of the hybrid storage configuration.

Did you complete the EC user questionnaire available at <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/RIsurveyUSERS> ? (necessary)

Yes No

Feedback – HSE, Ethics and Satisfaction

Please rate on a scale from 1 (excellent) to 5 (poor). Feel free to provide additional comments

Practical information on how to apply for Transnational Access and the overall application process

1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

[Comment]

Information provided, once your project was accepted, on how to proceed

1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

[Comment]

Support received at the site(s) regarding technical/scientific matters and logistics

Have you got sufficient support from the RI staff during the project? If not, please, specify the problems. Yes No

[Please specify any problems]

RI extension / upgrades required

In your opinion, is the RI needed to be upgraded? If yes, please give an explanation.

Yes No

[Please specify]

Problems with local regulations

Have you had any problems with regulations of the visited RI owner (HSE, lab working hours, etc.)? If yes, please, specify

	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please specify]</i>	
Health and safety issues	Did you encounter any health or safety issue during your research? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to the environment, to animals or plants? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Environment & Ethics	Did your research deal with endangered fauna and/or flora and/or protected areas? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to humans, including research staff? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Environment & Ethics – Dual use	Does your research have the potential for military applications? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Environment & Ethics – Misuse	Does your research have the potential for malevolent /criminal/terrorist abuse? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Environmental issues	Were any potentially dangerous substances (materials / gases etc.) released into the environment (atmosphere, water, or land)? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	

Ethics issues	Are there any other ethics issues that should be taken into consideration? Please specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please provide details]</i>					
Overall impression of communication and interaction after finishing your TNA related work	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>[Comment]</i>					
Suggestions for facilities not included in StoRIES which you would use for your research					
<i>[Please provide suggestions for specific type of facilities missing (RI gaps) or measurement / experiments you would like to perform which cannot be done on current StoRIES facilities]</i>					
Suggestions how StoRIES can improve future TNA programme, how to make the TNA more impactful on the energy storage technologies and how to enable the achievement of high TRL levels.					
<i>[Your suggestions]</i>					
Feedback – Pro-active Innovation Support					
Awareness	Did you know about the pro-active innovation support of StoRIES. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please specify how you learned about the pro-active innovation support]</i>					
Personal experience	Have you taken advantage of or benefited from the pro-active innovation support? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please provide details]</i>					
Information/service provided by the pro-active innovation support?	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>[Please provide details]</i>					

I declare that the above provided information and especially that information on the number of days visited the RI is correct.

